

liberation of three protons according to equation (3).

$$K = \frac{[C][H^+]^3}{[M^{3+}][H_3TML]} \quad \dots (4)$$

The negative logarithms of the equilibrium constants for all these thiomalates are calculated by equation (4) according to the method followed in the investigation of cadmium citrate complex⁴. The mean values of $-\log K$ are found to be 12.72 ± 0.16 , 12.21 ± 0.09 , 11.55 ± 0.2 , 11.28 ± 0.14 , 11.23 ± 0.16 , 11.17 ± 0.11 , 11.15 ± 0.1 and 11.1 ± 0.06 for lanthanum, cerium, praseodymium, neodymium, samarium, gadolinium, dysprosium and holmium, respectively.

The results show that the relative order of stability for the thiomalate complexes studied in the present investigations is La(III) < Ce(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III) < Sm(III) < Gd(III) < Dy(III) < Ho(III). The relative stability of these rare earth chelates increases with the decrease in the crystal radii indicating the formation of predominantly ionic complexes. The stabilities of rare earth thiomalate complexes are found to be less than those of malate complexes⁵. This corresponds to the relative order of stability as $-\text{OH} > -\text{SH}$. This is in accordance with the order reported by Rossotti⁶ and Calvin and Martell⁷.

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Some Square Planar Complexes of N-4-Methyl-7-Hydroxy-8-Acetocoumarinylidene Anthranilic Acid with Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+}

G. P. POKHARIYAL*

Chemical Laboratories, M. M. College, Khakra-201 101

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COMPLEXES of the composition $\text{H}[\text{M}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_5)\cdot\text{Cl}]$ [$\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{2+}$, Pd^{2+} or Pt^{2+}] with N-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumarinylidene anthranilic acid (H_3MHACAA) have been studied. Analytical, magnetic, ir and electronic spectral data show that all these complexes possess square planar configuration.

Experimental

4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl coumarin was prepared¹ and N-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumarinylidene anthranilic acid, a tridentate ligand, was prepared by refluxing a mixture of 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl coumarin and anthranilic acid in ethanol in presence of a few drops of glacial acetic acid on water bath for 5.0 hr^{2,3}, yield 75%, m.p. 155°. (Found : C, 66.80 ; H, 4.30 ; N, 4.00. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_5$; C, 67.65 ; H, 4.45 ; N, 4.15%). 75% ethanolic solutions of the ligand were used throughout. Metal chlorides of A. R. quality were used.

The complexes of Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+} were isolated by refluxing a stoichiometric mixture of metal chloride and ligand in ethanol solution on the water bath for 2.5-4.5 hr. On refrigeration for a few days the reaction mixture yielded brown, grey and yellow crystals of the complexes which were washed with water, ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum, yield 60-70%, decomposition point 180-213°.

The complexes were analysed for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen on Thomas CH Analyser-35 and Colemann N-Analyser-29 at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Copper was determined by titration with EDTA using fast sulphon black indicator⁴. The metals, Pd and Pt, were determined gravimetrically as DMG or ammonium chloroplatinate complexes.

(a) $\text{H}[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_5)\cdot\text{Cl}]$, brown compound. (Found : C, 52.20 ; H, 3.00 ; N, 3.08 ; Cl, 8.03 ; Cu, 14.29. Calcd. ; C, 52.41 ; H, 3.21 ; N, 3.21 ; Cl, 8.16 ; Cu, 14.58%).

(b) $\text{H}[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_5)\cdot\text{Cl}]$, grey compound. (Found : C, 47.63 ; H, 2.73 ; N, 2.69 ; Cl, 7.25 ; Pd, 22.07. Calcd. ; C, 47.78 ; H, 2.92 ; N, 2.92 ; Cl, 7.42 ; Pd, 22.26%).

(c) $\text{H}[\text{Pt}(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_5)\cdot\text{Cl}]$, yellow compound. (Found : C, 40.00 ; H, 2.30 ; N, 2.28 ; Cl, 6.09 ;

*Address for correspondence—Dr. G. P. Pokhariyal, Sulbha Niwas, Near Oriental Bank, P.O. Khakra-201 101, Meerut, U. P.

Pt, 34.32. Calcd.; C, 40.24; H, 2.47; N, 2.47; Cl, 6.26; Pt, 34.42%.

Magnetic studies of the complexes were made on Guoy balance using mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato-cobaltate(II) as a standard. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in nujal mull on a Cary-14 recording spectrophotometer and the ir spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer, Model-577 Infracord spectrophotometer in CsI medium.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data reveal 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry in all cases. The effective magnetic moment 1.83 B.M. of the Cu^{2+} complex indicates the presence of one unpaired electron suggesting a square planar structure for the complex. The excess over the spin only value of 1.73 B. M. may be due to the presence of spin orbit coupling on John-Teller distortion^{5,6}. The solution spectrum of $\text{H}[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_8)\text{Cl}]$ shows a broad band maximum around 18500 cm^{-1} with a shoulder around 14300 cm^{-1} . The other bands observed are ~ 20000 and 35250 cm^{-1} . The band around 18500 cm^{-1} is diagnostic of square planar Cu^{2+} complex. The following tentative assignments ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$ (14300 cm^{-1}) and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ (18500 cm^{-1}) can be made⁷. The appearance of the 27000 cm^{-1} band is considered to be due to a symmetry for hidden transition^{8,9}. The higher energy band around 35250 cm^{-1} is due to intraligand charge transfer.

The complexes of Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+} are diamagnetic as expected. The electronic spectra of Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+} complexes show bands around 19500 , 24500 , 30000 cm^{-1} and 16850 , 20300 and 24500 cm^{-1} , respectively. These bands may be assigned to the transitions ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{A}_{2g}$, ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$, ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{E}_g$ in an increasing order of energy suggesting square planar environment around the metal atom^{10,11}. The bands at 48000 cm^{-1} in the case of Pd^{2+} complex, the a_{1g} (Z^2) level, moved to higher energy relative to the corresponding Pt^{2+} complex. The other band at 48000 cm^{-1} has also shifted to red with respect to Pt^{2+} complex and has been assigned to the transition ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow \text{C}^1\text{E}_g$.

Infrared spectral studies : A strong band around 3500 cm^{-1} occurs in the ir spectra of ligand which is assigned to νOH^{H} . The νOH bands are absent in the spectra of the complexes suggesting that the OH group of the ligand participates in complex formation. The high intensity band around 1700 cm^{-1} in the ligand can be assigned to the $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ mode. These bands are observed at almost the same position in the complexes ruling out the involvement of carbonyl group of ligand in complexation. The considerable fall in the intensity and frequency of $\nu\text{CH}_2-\text{C}=\text{N}$ -band (ligand $\sim 1625\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and complexes $\sim 1575\text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicate the M-N bonding¹². Further, the appearance of the bands in the regions $410-485\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $490-$

525 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of the chelates due to the formation of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ bonds indicates complex formation through nitrogen and oxygen donor of subsequent groups. The band in the region $290-330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned to the terminal $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})^{\text{H}}$.

Based on the above observations the following structure can be proposed for the complexes.

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